

WAYS OF IMPROVING COMPREHENSION SKILL.

Kosimova Dilobar Tursunaliyevna

an English teacher in Academic Lyceum
of Tashkent State University of Economics
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10648754>

Annotation: This article provide information about speaking that is one of the skills that students need to acquire when learning English. Speech is an important means of communication. Additionally, this article is about ways of speaking skill with technology

Key words: comprehension, speaking skill, pronunciation, spelling

Improving your speaking skills can be helpful in a wide range of social circumstances. Here, we look at the importance of speaking skills, and how to develop them. Speaking is something that everyone does to some extent or other. The average person might expect to utter thousands of words on any given day. Some working environments, however, require much more. If you improve your speaking skills, you'll find that all kinds of doors may suddenly open for you.

Unfortunately, effective speaking skills are too often regarded as something that you either have or you don't. As a result, many of us settle into accepting a certain level of speaking ability and remain there. But it is certainly possible to become a better speaker, and there are plenty of strategies you can employ to take your speaking skills to the next level.

So, exactly how might we develop our speaking skills? The answer usually involves incremental improvement that is supported by helpful habits. Let's look at a few of those habits.

1. Pronounce words correctly

Several words in English are notorious for tripping people up when it comes to pronunciation. Commonly mispronounced words include hyperbole, epitome, espresso, viscount, and mischievous. You can risk embarrassment if you get these wrong, even if many people do so. This is especially important if you're pronouncing words incorrectly during job interviews.

Being able to pronounce the words you're speaking will establish your authority, and eliminate miscommunication. Pronouncing words correctly will give you confidence, and also give your listeners confidence that you know what you are talking about.

2. Listen to spoken English

Listening to a language is the primary means through which we learn to speak it. This generally applies in adulthood as well as childhood. When it comes to the availability of the spoken word, we've never had it so good. With podcasts, audiobooks, talk radio, and television, you can easily absorb hours of English every day, and develop an ear for the language.

You should listen to the kind of material you'd like to replicate. Suppose you want to have productive discussions with colleagues. In that case, listening to informed debates between informed people might be a useful approach. If you want to be a bit more expressive, then listening to improvisational comedy, drama, or poetry might be the path to take. Chasing Time's courses on learning English through TV drama will help you to do this effectively.

3. Read aloud

One exercise that's always worthwhile is to read something out loud. Many seasoned writers recommend this as part of the editing process. If a sentence sounds good out loud, then it's probably a good sentence.

Additionally, reading aloud will allow you to practice and even troubleshoot your speaking skills. If there are specific phrases that you're constantly tripping over, then there's nowhere to hide when you're reading aloud.

The practice might also help with your [pacing](#), and your ability to [speak at a natural rate](#).

You don't have to do all your reading aloud. It might be considered slightly intrusive if you're doing it on a crowded train. But the benefits are tangible, so setting aside a portion of your reading time for out-loud practice might be highly desirable.

4. Learn to sing

By learning to sing, you'll pick up a range of skills that can also be applied to more everyday conversation and speech. You'll know when and how to project your voice, become more aware of what's going on physiologically, and get the confidence that comes with performing in front of people.

5. Learn to act

In a similar vein, learning to act can confer many benefits, even if it's simply landing a supporting role in an amateur-dramatics society production. In addition, acting can help you to confront aspects of the language that you might not yet be familiar with. If you spend most of your time working with dry, technical concepts, then getting creative with the language might be more than worthwhile.

6. Get into poetry

Quite a few of us carry around preconceptions about poetry, which can get in the way of really enjoying and appreciating it. Unlike a novel or an essay, a poem is intended to be spoken aloud, in much the same way as song lyrics are meant to be sung. Getting to grips with the mechanics of what makes a good poem will help you speak more fluently.

For many of us, effective speaking skills don't always come easily. For some, they require work, patience, and determination. You can't expect to turn into an amazing orator overnight. Developing eloquence may take sustained effort, regular practice, and reinforcing helpful habits over years or even decades.

References:

1. Carnegie, D. (1962). The quick and easy way to effective speaking, Newyork: Association press.(pp.31-32).
2. Hedge,T. (2008). Teaching and learning in the language classroom,China: Oxford University Press.
3. Raqiboyevna, G. M. (2023). Hereditary Pigmentary Degeneration. American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149), 1(10), 146-149.
4. AMINOVA, Z., & KHALILOVA, O. MATERIALS IN ESP COURSES. Иностраные языки в Узбекистане. 2019 (3): 83-93.
5. Aminova, Z. P. (2020). THE ESSENTIAL ROLE OF IT IN INCREASING STUDENTS'MOTIVATION. Modern Science, (6-4), 90-92.
6. Aminova, Z. P. (2020). WORLD OF EDUCATION ARE USING ELECTRONIC PLATFORM SUCH AS MOODLE SYSTEM. Modern Science, (5-1), 276-278.
7. Aminova, Z. P. (2018). Importance of Implementing Pedagogical Technologies to Education System. Eastern European Scientific Journal, (2).
8. Хосиятов, Х. О. (2022). ҚАШҚАДАРЁ ВА СУРХОНДАРЁ ВИЛОЯТЛАРИ МУЗЕЙЛАРИНИНГ НУФУЗЛИ ХАЛҚАРО ТАШКИЛОТЛАР ВА ХОРИЖИЙ МАМЛАКАТЛАР БИЛАН АЛОҚАЛАРИ. Gospodarka i Innowacje., 28, 186-190.
9. Хосиятов, Х. О. (2020). МУСТАҚИЛЛИК ЙИЛЛАРИДА ТЕРМИЗ АРХЕОЛОГИЯ МУЗЕЙИ. ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ, (SI-1№ 4).
10. Khosiyatov, K. O. (2020). ВЛИЯНИЕ КРАЕВЕДЧЕСКОГО МУЗЕЯ В КАРШИ НА ДУХОВНОСТЬ МОЛОДЁЖИ. Theoretical & Applied Science, (6), 686-692.
11. Tursunnazarova, E. T. (2022). THE USE OF LITERATURE IN THE LANGUAGE CLASSROOM. THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD, 1(2), 196-200.

12. Yusubjonova, M. I., Vallamatova, S. S., & Tursunnazarova, E. T. (2022). CONSECUTIVE TRANSLATION AND ITS PECULARITIES. THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD, 1(2), 50-55.
13. Agytaevna, A. G. (2023). FUNCTION OF LANGUAGE IN PRESERVATION OF NATIONAL ETHNO-CULTURAL INFORMATION (on the example of materials of the Kazakh language). American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development, 16, 151-156.
14. Gazizova, L. K., & Ermatova, B. O. (2023). SOME ASPECTS OF AGE-RELATED MACULAR DEGENERATION. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 2(13), 28-34.
15. Gazizova, L. K., & Ermatova, B. O. Prevention of Age-Related Macular Degeneration. SCHOLASTIC: Journal of Natural and Medical Education.
16. Ermatova, B. O., & Gazizova, L. K. (2023). RELEVANCE OF OPEN ANGLE GLAUCOMA IN ELDERLY PEOPLE. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(21), 26-31.
17. Uralovna, B. Z., & Ravshan o'g'li, A. Y. (2023). Hozirgi o'zbek she'riyatida badiiy ko'chimlarning obyektiv va subyektiv asoslari. Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari, 2(2), 9-15.
18. Uralovna, B. Z. (2023). The Place of the Uzbek Language in the World Community. Genius Repository, 25, 35-37.
19. Kaipbergenova, S. (2024). APPROACHES IN COMPUTER LINGUADIDACTICS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES USING NETWORK TECHNOLOGIES. Models and methods in modern science, 3(1), 255-257.
20. FAYZULLAEVA, S. U. THEMATIC DIRECTIONS OF THE NATURE OF THE LYRICAL EVENING. THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука, (5), 157-159.
21. Isakovna, I. R. (2023). LITERARI THE ROLE OF IMAGE ENHANCEMENT TECHNIQUES IN THE PROGRESS. International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 3(07), 48-52.
22. Gafurov, B. Z. (2019). RESEARCH OF SEGMENTAL BACKGROUND VALUES OF NAMES OF EXISTING UZBEK LANGUAGE WHICH BEGIN FROM THE AGREEMENT LETTER "K". Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 1(6), 272-274.
23. Zakirovich, G. B. (2022). Discourse about the peculiarities of the theme of male gender in advertising texts in Russian and Uzbek (on the material of medical vocabulary). EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE, 2(2), 4-8.

24. Zakirovich, G. B. (2022). Discourse about the peculiarities of the theme of male gender in advertising texts in Russian and Uzbek (on the material of medical vocabulary). *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 2(2), 4-8.
25. Бабаева, Г. (2022). Маданиятлараро мулоқот жараёнидаги муомала маданияти. *Современные лингвистические исследования: зарубежный опыт, перспективные исследования и инновационные методы преподавания языков*, (1), 208-209.
26. Хакимов, М. Ш., Маткулиев, У. И., Ашуров, Ш. Э., & Кодирова, Г. Р. (2022). Новый взгляд на оценку тяжести кровотечения из варикозно расширенных вен пищевода (Doctoral dissertation, Узбекистан).
27. Ашурова, О. Ю., & Кодирова, Г. Р. (2020). ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ЭНТЕРАЛЬНОЙ ОКСИГЕНОТЕРАПИИ (КИСЛОРОДНОГО КОКТЕЙЛЯ) В КОМПЛЕКСНОМ ВОССТАНОВИТЕЛЬНОМ ЛЕЧЕНИИ ГИПОКСИИ И ХРОНИЧЕСКИХ БОЛЕЗНЕЙ ОРГАНОВ ДЫХАНИЯ. *Интернаука*, (46-1), 36-37.
28. Муртазаева, Ф. (2024). ЖЕНСКОЕ НАСИЛИЕ И ЕГО ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ ОТПЕЧАТОК В РОМАНЕ ЭМИЛИ БРОНТЕ «ГРОЗОВОЙ ПЕРЕВАЛ». *Interpretation and researches*, 2(1 (23)).
29. Муртазаева, Ф. Р. (2023). ВНУТРЕННИЙ МИР ЖЕНЩИН В АНГЛИЙСКОЙ «ЖЕНСКОЙ ПРОЗЕ». *Инновационные исследования в науке*, 2(10), 44-48.
30. Муртазаева, Ф. Р. (2023, August). ДИНАМИКА РАСКРЫТИЯ ПСИХОЛОГИЗМА В АМЕРИКАНСКОЙ «ЖЕНСКОЙ ПРОЗЕ». In *International Conference of Education, Research and Innovation* (Vol. 1, No. 7, pp. 15-19).
31. Aslam, M. (2003). *Teaching of english*. New Delhi: Foundation Book.